

Major insect pests of wetland rice in Guyana, South America.

Growth stage	Pest		Damage
	Scientific name	Common name	
Emergence to maximum tillering	1. <i>Helodytes foveolatus</i> Duval (Curculionidae: Coleoptera)	Rice water weevil	Larva feeds on roots. Adult feeds on eye of pre-germinated seeds.
	2. <i>Hydrellia deonieri</i> Rambajan (Ephydriidae: Diptera)	Rice leafminer Rice blackfly	Larva feeds in growing shoot, causes deadheart.
	3. <i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i> (Smith) (Noctuidae: Lepidoptera)	Fall armyworm	Larva feeds on seedling leaves, causes burnt tip, later defoliation.
	4. <i>Mocis punctularis</i> Hubner (Noctuidae: Lepidoptera)	Rice looper	
	5. <i>Neoconocephalus</i> Spp. <i>Caulopsis</i> Spp. (Tettigoniidae: Orthoptera)	Long-horned grass-hopper	Feeds on leaves that appear shredded, cobweb.
Panicle initiation to heading	1. <i>Caulopsis cupsidata</i> Scudder (Tettigoniidae: Orthoptera)	Long-horned grass-hopper	Feeds on leaves and ball, causes whitehead.
Heading to hard dough	1. <i>Oebalus poecilus</i> Dallas (Pentatomidae: Hemiptera)	Stink bug or paddy bug	Nymph and adult feed on grains at milk stage, cause wind paddy or atrophied glumes; at dough stage cause broken barrels, discolored rice after milling.
Hard dough to harvest, storage	1. <i>Sitotroga cerealella</i> (Olivier) (Gelechiidae: Lepidoptera)	Angoumois grain moth	Larva feeds on kernel.
	2. <i>Rhyzopertha dominica</i> (Fabricius) (Bostrichidae: Coleoptera)	Lesser grain borer	

Rice gall midge incidence in the dry season

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Rice gall midge (*Orseolia oryzae*), a major insect pest in late-planted fields in the wet season (May-November) in the Andhra Pradesh Krishna and Godavari deltas, has become a major problem in the dry season (November-April) in the Godavari delta since 1978. The percentage silver shoots or galls recorded in

Percent silver shoots in dry season, Maruteru, India.

Trial	Silver shoots (%)			
	1979		1980	
	Mean	Maximum	Mean	Maximum
Uniform Variety Trial 2	11	20	5	8
Uniform Variety Trial 3	17	24	18	25
Uniform Variety Trial 4	16	28	13	8

coordinated variety trials show the high pressure of gall midge at Maruteru center (see table).

It is likely that extensive use of pesticides to control insects has resulted in the destruction of predators and parasites of

rice gall midge. Popular *rabi season* varieties Jaya, Prabhat, Prakash, Rasi, and Tella Hamsa are susceptible to rice gall midge. BPT1235 and IR36 are promising early-maturing, gall midge-resistant varieties. ■

Effects of rice plant age on diopsis oviposition and plant susceptibility

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Diopsis thoracica (West), a serious pest limiting rice yields in West Africa, prefers plants of particular ages for oviposition. Confirmation of the specific age range would be useful in planning pest management programs involving host plant resistance and other control measures.

Pregerminated seeds of 2 rice varieties

Diopsis thoracica eggs laid on rice plants of different ages and subsequent development of dead-hearts in Sierra Leone.^a

DT ^b	IR5			GH106-76		
	Eggs (no.)	Dead-hearts (no.)	Dead-hearts/egg (no.)	Eggs (no.)	Dead-hearts (no.)	Dead-hearts/egg (no.)
10	4 cd	6 b	1.5	2 ab	4 ab	2.0
20	11 ab	13 a	1.2	2 ab	3 b	1.5
30	14 a	14 a	1.0	5 a	6 a	1.2
40	8 bc	6 b	0.8	3 ab	3 b	1.0
50	2 d	2 c	1.0	1 b	0	0.0
60	1 d	0 c	0.0	0 b	0	0.0

^aTotal of 6 replications. In the same column, means followed by the same letter do not differ at the 1% level of probability. ^bDT = days after transplanting.

with similar tillering abilities, IR5 and GH106-76, were sown at 10-day intervals. Seedlings 21 days after sowing

(DS) were transplanted separately at 2 seedlings/pot. Rice plants 60, 50, 40, 30, 20, and 10 days after transplanting (DT)

were exposed to *Diopsis thoracica* (25 males and 25 females) in a wooden cage for 3 days to allow egg laying. The eggs laid per pot were counted. Ten days after the eggs hatched, deadhearts were

counted.

The most eggs and deadhearts were recorded on plants 20-40 DT (see table). In both varieties, 30-day-old plants recorded the highest number of eggs and

deadhearts. The rate of deadheart development was fastest in 10- to 30-day-old plants. Virtually no eggs were laid or deadhearts developed on 60-day-old plants. ■

Effect of intensity of light on the predacious green mirid bug

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The green mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter is a predator on the eggs and early-stage nymphs of brown planthoppers (BPH) and green leafhoppers (GLH). Its number is large in the light traps and in the field during September-October when the activity of BPH and GLH is very high.

The effect of light intensity on attracting this predator was studied using incandescent lights of different intensities from October 1980 to February

Mirid bugs trapped with lights of 4 intensities, 1980-81, Tamil Nadu, India.

	Mirid bugs trapped (no.)				Total
	15 watts	40 watts	60 watts	100 watts	
October	543	1156	1570	3670	6939
November	11	120	156	474	761
December	9	75	48	194	326
January	1	16	42	66	125
February	-	1	5	7	13
Total	564	1368	1821	4411	-

1981 (see table).

The mirid bug was very active during October, when the numbers of BPH and GLH were also high (BPH 21,174; GLH 11,928). Predator incidence was positively correlated with populations of BPH and GLH. The mirid bug population then declined and reached very low levels during February, when activity of

the two insect pests also was low (BPH 129, GLH 17).

With increased light intensity, there was a corresponding increase in the catch of pests and predators. But high wattage in the light trap removed bio-control agents from rice fields. Rice pests can be monitored with low wattage bulbs. ■

Esterases and malathion resistance in brown planthopper

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The 4th and 5th instars of the brown planthopper (BPH) were used in the bioassay to determine the effect of *S,S,S*-tributyl phosphorotrithioate (DEF), an esterase inhibitor, on toxicity of malathion and of two other organophosphorus insecticides against a malathion-resistant (R) strain of BPH. DEF enhanced malathion toxicity 20 times, methyl parathion toxicity 6 times, and parathion 11 times (see table).

This implies that detoxification mediated by these esterases is associated with insecticide resistance in the BPH.

Spectrophotometric determination of esterase activity in BPH males with different levels of malathion resistance showed a linear relationship between esterase activity and log-resistance ratio (see figure). Similar reactions have been reported for the green rice leafhopper and the smaller BPH. ■

Effect of DEF on susceptibility to 3 insecticides of a malathion-resistant (R) brown planthopper strain, Taiwan.

Insecticide	RR ^a	LC ₅₀ (mg/ml)		SR ^b
		Alone	With DEF	
Malathion	484	11.13	0.56	19.9
Methyl parathion	35	1.00	0.17	5.9
Parathion	141	2.67	0.24	11.1

^aResistance ratio = LC₅₀ of resistant strain divided by LC₅₀ of susceptible strain. ^bSynergistic ratio = LC₅₀ of insecticide divided by LC₅₀ of insecticide with DEF (*S,S,S*-tributyl phosphorotrithioate).

Resistance ratio

α-naphthyl acetate (μmol/ 10 min per mg).